

COVID-19: Transition to Online Problem-based Learning in Robotics – Challenges, Opportunities and Insights

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Abstract

This research in progress reports on the challenges, opportunities and insights gained regarding an introductory robotics course during a rapid transition to an online learning environment during the COVID-19 lockdown. The Fourth Industrial Revolution is a major driving force for change across the globe. It is characterised by developments, such as 3D printing, artificial intelligence and robotics. As a result, there is a need to prepare students to develop specific skills for future demands. The aim of the course is to introduce fourth-year Computer Science Education students to robotics while employing problem-based learning online as teaching–learning approach. Opportunities are provided for the development of essential skills, such as cooperative problem solving and self-directed learning. The robotics course comprises various topics, such as a historical overview, ethical considerations, as well as the requirement of students to program Lego® Mindstorms robots online using relevant software and simulation programs. In the study, some tasks were completed individually while others had to be done in teams. A qualitative methodology was used. Data collection consisted of the lecturer’s self-reflective notes as well as students’ weekly reflective sheets regarding their responsibilities and activities, and the submission of a comprehensive portfolio regarding all programming codes, pictorial evidence of robot simulations and short video recordings of team collaboration. All students’ data were submitted on the university’s learning platform or course management system as well as on a cloud. The data were analysed manually. Based on the reflections and feedback, the lecturer gained insight into the online teaching and learning of robotics. Further, results indicate that students developed essential skills as they were challenged with online learning.

Keywords: Computer Science Education Students; Online Learning; Problem-based Learning; Robotics.

1 Introduction

The first reported outbreak of coronavirus disease (COVID-19 or SARS-CoV-2) was in Wuhan, China in December 2019. Although the origin of this severe acute respiratory syndrome virus is not known, the global impact thereof is unprecedented (Del Rio & Malani, 2020). Currently, the global infection of the coronavirus pandemic exceeds 11.7 million and 540 000 deaths have been reported (7 July 2020). Further, there is no vaccine currently available, testing is insufficient and it appears to be possible that some individuals may even be “asymptomatic” carriers of the virus (Del Rio & Malani, 2020, p. 1339). As a result, most countries declared a so-called “quarantine” or “lockdown” period to implement particular protocols with the aim to prevent the rapid spreading of the virus with resultant infection and possible death of individuals. Moreover, the lockdown affects all levels of humankind. For example, many universities and schools closed due to an emergency call from heads of state. Such a call has a critical impact on students’ learning. This required a rapid transition from full-time learning to online learning during lockdown without losing the benefits of active and responsible learning.

Learning should be driven by using appropriate pedagogies and approaches where students are actively involved, curious and searching for innovative answers to open-ended problems (Yiannoutsou, Nikitopoulou, Kynigos, Gueorguiev, & Fernandez, 2017). Problem-based learning (PBL) is an approach that encapsulates student-centred learning, active participation and high-level thinking (Savery, 2015). At the core of PBL is the drive to solve unknown, open-ended or vague problems in collaboration and to think about solutions in new ways. However, due to the abovementioned limitations imposed by the COVID-19 lockdown, the challenge was to explore how to apply PBL in an online environment to introduce full-time Computer Science Education students to robotics. Consequently, the aim of this research was to report on the challenges, opportunities and insights gained regarding an introductory robotics course due to a rapid transition to online PBL.

2 Context and related work

This section outlines the online learning environment and PBL as well as the learning of robotics.

2.1 Problem-based practice

Mohd-Yusof (2017, p. 18) notes that the PBL approach can challenge both the lecturer and the student, as the lecturer is not “going to teach everything that students need to learn”. Lecturers need to formulate suitable and authentic problems, guide students to understand the PBL approach, facilitate for active learning and team cooperation, and scaffold students to address challenges and support for metacognitive and critical thinking (Mohd-Yusof, 2017). Likewise, students should clarify and understand nuances of the problem, clearly formulate learning goals, conduct research, explore challenges, and come up with innovative solutions to an ill-defined problem (Baloche & Brody, 2017; Savery, 2015). The aim is not only to solve the problem in hand but also to develop self-directed learning (SDL) skills and essential attributes for the future to address unknown problems and challenges in integrated disciplines that affect society.

2.2 Online problem-based learning

Applying PBL in an online environment is not trivial. Abdullah and Kian (2019) applied PBL where industry experts were involved in online scaffolding to assist engineering students in developing essential high-order skills for the workplace. Valiente et al. (2019) used an online simulation tool (circuit simulation applet in Java) to enhance engineering students’ learning of electronics. However, Blayone, Van Oostveen, Barber, DiGiuseppe, and Childs (2017) put forward a social-constructivist model with relevance to PBL and inquiry-based learning in online contexts. The Fully Online Learning Community model (FOLC) accentuates the construction of knowledge (*knowing*), development of competencies to solve complex problems together (*acting*), and a community that relates to transformative learning, which involves trust, openness, exploring of different views, collaboration and feedback, among others (*being*) (Blayone et al., 2017; Gray, 2016). (Note that the words in brackets and in italics indicate alignment of aspects of FOLC with the three elements of curricula as mentioned by Kolmos (2017) in the context of transition to a PBL curriculum). FOLC endorses social presence (SP) and cognitive presence (CP) as means of responsible and shared experiences to accomplish joint tasks online. SP relates to the ability of a student to be involved and interacting purposefully in an online community of learning while CP involves an individual constructing meaning in authentic settings through online environments (Blayone et al., 2017). In addition, Blayone et al. (2017) highlight that “successful collaborative learning” occurs at the intersection of SP and CP where learners develop essential competencies to address “critical inquiry” (Blayone et al., 2017, p. 4). Schultze and Brooks (2019, p. 709) concur that SP involves the existence of “being there” in a virtual world, to be committed to act and become deeply involved. Such learning is in particular a challenge in subjects with a practical component, for instance Science, Engineering, Technology and Computer Science.

2.3 Online learning of robotics

One of the fields of specialisation, related to the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), is robotics. Schwab (2016, p. 10) gives prominence to the 4IR and refers to the “growing harmonization and integration of so many different disciplines and discoveries”, and mentions robotics among others. Using robots may have an effect on supply chains and all sectors to perform an array of tasks involving precision, time and quality and could add value to society (Schwab, 2016). Consequently, there is a need that individuals should be exposed to robotics, particularly in the education sector. In 2019, the South African Minister of Basic Education announced the development and implementation of a new curriculum in 2021–2022 in schools regarding “Coding and Robotics” (IOL, 2019). To stay informed, lecturers decided to prepare Computer Science Education students for demands that might arise in the future, such as robotics. As a result, Computer Science pre-service education students should gain knowledge and skills to plan activities and to assemble and program robots.

Avello, Lavonen, and Zapata-Ros (2020) outline the relationship between coding and robotics and computational and creative thinking. Computational thinking is essential for the development of particular skills, and involves the understanding of problem scenarios, the development of computer programs and digital competences, as well as human activities involved in collaborative problem solving. Based on their

research, Avello et al. (2020, p. 1) noted, “computational and creative thinking are related to find efficient and good solution to problems”. Likewise, Pollak and Ebner (2019) emphasise computational thinking in terms of understanding the problem context, application of relevant skills, strategies (e.g. break down a problem in manageable sections) and computational tools. In an online learning environment, some tools can be used to assist in the learning of robotics. All of these have different approaches, for example:

- LEGO Mindstorms EV3 is software to program third-generation robots and enables an individual to connect and control the LEGO EV3 brick using USB, Bluetooth or Wi-Fi (Figure 1);
- LEGO Digital Designer is simulation software used to design and build a robot (Lego) (Figure 2);
- CoderZ provides a visual code editor with an EV3 online simulator (CoderZ, 2019) (Figure 3a, 3b); and
- Ev3_scratch uses Scratch code in the browser to command the EV3 robot to move over Bluetooth.

Figure 1. Mindstorms EV3 visual code segment.

Figure 2. LEGO Digital Designer simulation software.

Figure 3a. Visual code editor in CoderZ.

Figure 3b. EV3 online simulator in CoderZ.

Due to the rapid transition from full-time to online learning without losing the benefits of active and responsible learning, using appropriate environments for an introduction to robotics was imperative. The following research question directed this research: What are the challenges, opportunities and insights associated with a rapid transition to an online problem-based learning (PBL) environment for robotics?

3 Empirical Research

This section outlines the participants, the online learning management system (LMS) as well as data collection and analysis procedures.

3.1 Participants

Fourth-year Computer Science Education students participated in this research. The population consisted of three full-time students only. Although, this was an excellent opportunity to introduce and implement robotics using an online PBL approach, the aim was to refine activities for a larger population of distance students (using online learning) who will be introduced to robotics in another course in the next semester.

3.2 Online learning management system (LMS)

The lecturer (author) restructured the course to enable students to achieve the outcomes using online PBL. The students were required to manage and upload their assignments (PBL robotics tasks) on the eFundi university learning management platform (developed by Sakai) (Figure 4). In addition, students used WhatsApp to share information (social and cognitive presence) and the lecturer provided additional support regarding some

challenges that students experienced with the simulation programs (teacher presence). Particular robotic scenarios were 'drivers' for active learning and group work that required problem solving, critical thinking and innovation while employing the PBL approach. Further, opportunities were provided for cooperative problem solving and the development of SDL. Students participated in an online learning community using Zoom (online discussion through a cloud-based platform) and submitted their assignments on eFundi as PDF files to enable online assessment using electronic marking tools. Figure 4 outlines the time schedule and due dates on eFundi.

eFundi		View Site As:				
Site Info	Assignment Title	For	Status	Open	Due	
Assignment 5e: Program and move a robot Edit Duplicate View Submissions	Entire Site	Closed	28-May-2020 12:10	07-Jun-2020 17:00		
Assignment 5d: Program a robot Edit Duplicate View Submissions	Entire Site	Closed	18-May-2020 18:00	03-Jun-2020 17:00		
Assignment 5c: Build a robot Edit Duplicate View Submissions	Entire Site	Closed	18-May-2020 17:05	03-Jun-2020 17:00		
Assignment 5b: Robotics theory Edit Duplicate View Submissions	Entire Site	Closed	05-May-2020 22:35	23-May-2020 17:00		
Assignment 5a: Robotics theory Edit Duplicate View Submissions	Entire Site	Closed	05-May-2020 22:35	15-May-2020 17:00		

Figure 4. eFundi learning management system.

3.3 Problem-based tasks and student activities

PBL tasks and students' responsibilities were worded as follows: you need to work individually on some tasks while others are group work. Download the LEGO Mindstorms software as well as the CoderZ simulator program. Study the YouTube videos (some links were given by the lecturer) to assist you in using these programming environments. (Note, with the rendering problem of robotics parts, students could not complete Assignment 5c online using Lego Digital Designer [Figure 2]).

- *Task 5d: LEGO Mindstorms environment* (similar to Figure 1). Each student needed to do the programming on his or her own to get used to the software environment. In this case, the task was worded as follows, "[m]ove the robot until the light sensor identifies the green line, then turn 90 degrees left, move forward until an obstacle is detected ... " Since you do not have a real robot (EV3 brick), you need to visualise the movements and test your programming code. After completion, all students should work together as a team. Use a platform, such as Zoom, to share your work. Each student uploads his or her code. Select among yourselves the task with the 'correct' programming code. Then brainstorm and elaborate on the code to perform particular movements on which your team has decided. Explain in a Word document the approach and/or steps that you have followed to test the programming code. Continuously reflect on and evaluate your final programming code.
- *Task 5e: CoderZ simulator* (similar to Figure 3a and 3b). Each student needs to program and move his or her own robot using the simulator. This is an open-ended problem. After completion of your program, cooperate in a team. Each student uploads his or her video on WhatsApp. Subsequently, your team needs to select the 'best' example and add some functionality. Collaborate on WhatsApp, justify your modifications and copy the screen prints (evidence of conversations and images) into Word. Continuously reflect on and evaluate your final programming code.
- Do the following in both tasks 5d and 5e:
 - Make video recordings of your programming efforts using your mobile phone. In addition, make screen prints of the programming code (diagrams).
 - After finalising these tasks, each student must complete the weekly reflective sheet template (comprising questions on responsibilities, cooperation, commitment, time management, addressing of challenges and peer assessment).

- Copy the programming code (screen print) to a Word document and number each task consecutively. Include the explanation of your program, testing approach and the steps that you followed as well as additional programming tasks, weekly reflective sheets and images, and submit these as a PDF file on eFundi. Also submit your short video recordings as zipped files. Note that time slots are set for each PBL task.
- Reflective questions: scan the QR code as a link to Google Docs and complete a short questionnaire regarding your experiences, team cooperation, approaches and insight on the online programming of robots.

3.4 Data collection an analysis

Date collection involved the PDF documents comprising programming code, explanation of the testing approach and steps, additional programming tasks, weekly reflective sheets, images, additional reflections on Google Docs and short video recordings. Data were manually analysed and some themes emerged.

4 Results and discussion

This section presents the results and addresses the research question. Table 1 outlines the themes that emerged from the results. Participant numbers are indicated in brackets. Quotations are reproduced verbatim and unedited.

Table 1. Themes that emerged from the results.

Theme	Students' feedback
Team work	"My group and I discussed and assisted each other when we were not sure of something as well as to reassure each other and motivate each other to continue to find a solution and the right way into doing something. We worked fairly well together ... so the pace of discussion went well." (P1)
	"During this discussion, we had to make changes to the code, to allow the robot to work properly. All members were engaged and involved." (P2)
Challenges	"Only problems we really faced ... as 2 of the 3 people in the group did not have the same version in Mindstorms ..." (P1)
	"Programming without a robot is difficult to work with trial and error and to understand the type of programming at the beginning." (P3)
Reflection	"I kept trying to find new and better ways to program the code the way I wanted." (P2)
	"I personally think that we have achieved our own personal aims as well as group aims ... we discussed ... the videos and what we researched as well as programmed." (P1)
	"I really enjoyed doing this assignment. It is very nice that we need to work together as a team to improve on our work." (P2)
	"As a team, we have achieved our goals of programming the robot and doing what was required." (P3)
	"We used other 'parts' of code to get the robot to turn. We also decided on a different modification so that the colour sensor problem was not an issue anymore ... This has been very insightful and I hope to do it with the learners in my class some day." (P2)

"It was easier to think practically about the movements of the robot. We started with an easier application/software and built ourselves up to CoderZ. If we had immediately started with CoderZ, I would have been a lot more confused." (P2)

"PBL - students will remember the work a lot better if they have to solve the problems, instead of being spoon fed. They will also enjoy it more and be able to explore more. [...] It was something new and something I would never get the chance to do in any other subjects." (P2)

"That programming a robot is very fun and interesting to do. It challenged me to think out of the box." (P3)

Approach

"We first spoke about our programs, using whatsapp [...] use my programming, to work on as a team, seeing that my computer was the only one with the latest version of the LEGO Mindstorm application. On zoom, we went through each instruction [...] We asked questions about whether the correct blocks were used and whether they were being measured correctly." (P2)

"We had a ZOOM meeting to go through the program to see what works and what doesn't." (P3)

Evaluation

"We all agreed that the above programming was correct." (P2)

"Yes, our team has achieved its aims. We discussed the programming and came up with the best possible solution to the programming problem." (P2)

"Our team is progressing at a good pace. We talk about and determine deadlines for our assignments, meetings, discussions etc. and each member sticks to it." (P2)

Time

"We are progressing very well and we are ahead of schedule." (P3)

Resources

"Many YouTube tutorials watched to do the programs and to learn how to code." (P3)

The following question is addressed in this section: What are the challenges, opportunities and insights associated with a rapid transition to an online PBL environment for robotics?

Results indicate that students experienced several *challenges*. For example, they had to get used to the programming environment, some members did not have the same Mindstorms version, and initially it was difficult to do coding without a robot (Mindstorms EV3 brick) as they had to understand the programming code and the resultant robot movement. As a result, participants studied YouTube videos to assist them. Participants approached the problems as follows: they discussed the programs using WhatsApp to comment on one another's coding. Thereafter, they used Zoom, discussed each instruction and asked questions regarding the use of the correct programming blocks and their functionality. During Zoom meetings, students changed the programming code to ensure that the robot worked properly.

Regarding *opportunities*, participants experienced working in problem-based teams as positive in the sense that all members attended the meetings online, they were committed, shared their knowledge, improved their programming and contributed to the development of the final code. Further, they assisted each other, reassured and motivated each other to find a solution and worked well together. One student remarked, "I

personally think that we have achieved our own personal aims as well as group aims.” The team progressed at an acceptable pace and they were able to submit their assignments before the deadline.

Moreover, participants reflected before, during and after programming tasks. Students did some research, studied videos and worked through the requirements before commencing with the assignments. One participant said, “[d]uring this discussion, we had to make changes to the code, to allow the robot to work properly.” The outcomes were achieved and students assessed each other with average marks as follows: Participant 1 (9/10), P2 (10/10), and P3 (8/10).

In accordance with the FOLC model (see 2.2), examples of the construction of knowledge (*knowing*), cooperative solving of problems (*acting*) and community of practice (*being*) were identified where students collaborated online to address robotics tasks (Table 2).

Table 2. Application of the FOLC model in the online learning of robotics.

Principle	Selected examples
Construct knowledge	“We asked questions about whether the correct blocks were used and whether they were being measured correctly.”
	“We discussed the programming and came up with the best possible solution.” “PBL - students will remember the work alot better if they have to solve the problems, instead of being spoon fed. They will also enjoy it more and be able to explore more.” (cognitive presence)
Cooperate in solving problems	“We had a ZOOM meeting to go through the program to see what works and what doesn’t” “I personally think that we achieved our own personal aims as well as group aims.” (social presence).
	“This has been very insightful and I hope to do it with the learners in my class some day.”
Form a community of practice	“My group and I discussed and assisted each other ... reassure each other and motivate each other to continue to find a solution.” “We worked fairly well together.”

The lecturer developed some *insights* regarding the rapid transition from full-time to online learning:

- It is essential that full-time students should continue with the course online without losing the benefits of active and responsible learning.
- The lecturer should plan properly, provide clear expectations, and problems should be crafted for students in an online environment.
- Teacher’s presence is essential. The lecturer should facilitate, guide and assist students.
- Social and cognitive presence is crucial, particularly in an online PBL environment.
- Technical issues may be a challenge to ensure that all members use the same software; therefore, the lecturer should test the software on different platforms before students commence with the tasks.
- Members need to be actively involved in functioning teams where all contribute to solve the robotics problems in hand.
- Students should be committed and have to consider online learning as an opportunity for a community of practice.
- Compliance to PBL principles in an online learning environment is not trivial and students should be assisted in this regard.
- PBL as student-centred approach provides for the sharing and critical evaluation of ideas (*knowledge*).
- Online PBL activities should be student-driven and should involve active participation (*acting*).
- To counteract isolation, it is essential to provide for online collaboration (e.g. using Zoom or Microsoft Teams) in the sense of being present in enhancing one another’s learning (*being*).

5 Conclusion

The current research considered the challenges, opportunities and insights gained regarding an introductory robotics course due to a rapid transition to online PBL. Results indicate that, although students experienced some challenges, they were also exposed to new opportunities to collaborate online. Certain insights emerging from the rapid transition from full-time to online learning were gained to enhance responsible and active learning when introducing robotics to students. Limitations involved that only three students participated. Future research may involve the development and/or use of various platforms to optimise online PBL.

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